

Kinetics and mechanism of electron transfer reactions oxidation of mannitol by chromium(vi) in acid perchlorate medium

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Abstract : The kinetics of oxidation of mannitol (Mtol) by chromium(vi) in acid perchlorate medium has been studied. In oxidation of alcohol to aldehyde, when mannitol is sufficiently larger than oxidant, however, various products are formed, if the conditions are reversed. Ester as an intermediate is both kinetically and spectrophotometrically established. Chromium(vi) species have been discussed, and HCr^+O_3 species is expected to react with alcohol. The kinetic rate law is given by the eq. (1)

$$\frac{-d(\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}})}{dt} = \frac{kK[\text{HCrO}_4^-][\text{Mtol}][\text{H}^+]^2}{1 + K(\text{Mtol})} \quad (1)$$

where [Mtol] is for gross mannitol concentration.

Chloride ion inhibits the rate and this effect has been analysed quantitatively. A plausible reaction mechanism is proposed to account for the kinetic observations.

Keywords : Chromium(vi), kinetics, acid perchlorate, mannitol.

Chromium(vi) is frequently used in oxidimetric titrations as an analytical reagent. Chromic acid, aqueous solutions of dichromate, chromyl chloride, chromyl acetate and ditertiary butyl chromate are various other forms of chromium(vi) which have widely been employed in oxidations of a large number of organic and inorganic compounds both in acidic and alkaline solutions. This is probably the reason of exploring a large number of kinetic studies employing this oxidant to know much about the solution chemistry of chromium(vi). Various reviews¹⁻⁷ have appeared and chromium(vi) species with their pattern of reactivity are reported.

The oxidation of alcohols by chromium(vi) has been a subject of large number of studies until the hydride ion transfer mechanism was reported¹. However, disagreement with the mechanistic proposals⁸ made by Westheimer¹ exists⁴. These observations prompted us to undertake the title study from the following view points :

(a) The speciation of chromium(vi) is not yet well defined and still requires a better resolution of these species. (b) The hydrogen ion dependence observed in most of the reactions of chromium(vi) is complex owing to proton-dependent chromium(vi) species. The detailed analysis of these results can provide a reasonable portrait of the reaction events for proposition of the most probable reaction mechanism. (c) Anions such as chloride ion

drastically reduces the rates of chromium(vi) reaction, it is interesting to observe the effect of chloride ion in the title reaction where substrate species are not influenced by its presence.

Experimental

The details related to the preparation and standardization of various reagents employed in this study have already been reported elsewhere⁹. However, all other chemicals were either of AnalaR or guaranteed reagent grade and were used as supplied. Doubly distilled water was employed throughout the study. Reaction mixtures were prepared by mixing reagents of desired concentrations in glass-stoppered Erlenmeyer flasks which were immersed in a water-bath thermostated at 35 ± 0.1 °C unless stated otherwise. Chromium(vi) solution was taken in another flask and that too was also maintained at the same bath temperature. The reaction was initiated by adding the solution of chromium(vi) of the desired concentrations in the reaction mixtures and the time was recorded when half of the pipette contents were released into the reaction mixture. An aliquot sample (5 or 10 cm³) was withdrawn at different intervals of time and the remaining chromium(vi) was assayed iodometrically without any interference from other components of the reaction mixture. The kinetic measurements in triplicate were reproducible to within $\pm 6\%$.

Table 1. Initial rates (k_i), pseudo-first order rate constants (k') and second order rate constants (k) in the reaction of chromium(vi) and mannitol

$10^3 [\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]$ (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^2 [\text{Mtol}]$ (mol dm ⁻³)	(k_i) (mol dm ⁻³ s ⁻¹)	$10^4 (k')$ (s ⁻¹)	$10 k$ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)
3.0	2.0	1.8	–	3.0
3.5	2.0	2.1	–	3.0
4.0	2.0	2.6	–	3.3
4.5	2.0	2.9	–	3.20
5.0	2.0	3.3	–	3.3
6.0	2.0	3.8	–	3.2
7.0	2.0	4.3	–	3.1
8.0	2.0	5.2	–	3.3
10	2.0	6.3	–	3.1
1.0	5.0	–	17.9	3.6
1.5	5.0	–	17.9	3.6
2.0	5.0	–	17.9	3.6
2.5	5.0	–	17.9	3.6
3.0	5.0	–	17.9	3.6
3.5	5.0	–	18.4	3.7
4.0	5.0	–	18.4	3.7
4.5	5.0	–	17.0	3.6
5.0	5.0	–	18.4	3.7

The preliminary kinetics indicate disappearance of chromium(vi) to be a first order process and the pseudo-first order rate constants are independent of the gross initial concentrations of the oxidant eliminating any possibility of dimerization of chromium(vi). Initial rates were computed employing plane-mirror method¹⁰.

The stoichiometry of the reaction was determined taking excess of mannitol over chromium(vi) concentration. These reactions were allowed to occur in a thermostated water bath for *ca.* 12 h. The product was isolated as 2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazone derivative which on spectral analysis found to be an aldehyde. Such an observation corresponds to the reaction as represented by the eq. (1a).

Zyka *et al.*¹⁰ reported oxidation of mannitol by cobalt(III) in excess in acetic acid medium at higher than ambient temperature. This corresponded to the formation of formic acid and formaldehyde as represented by the eq. (1b)

Further oxidation (1–6 h) of these products does not take place if the temperature is ~40 °C and (25–95%) acetic acid. However, no such products were identified when mannitol was taken in large excess over chromium(vi). Thus the stoichiometry is different under different experimental conditions.

Fig. 1. A plot of (k') versus $[\text{H}^+]^2$: $[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm⁻³; $[\text{Mtol}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm⁻³; temp. = (O) 25 °; (Δ) 30 °; (\bullet) 35 ° and (\square) 40 °C.

Results

Chromium(vi) dependence : The concentration of chromium(vi) was varied in the range $(1.0\text{--}10.0) \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm⁻³ at constant concentrations of other reaction ingredients viz. $[\text{Mtol}] = 5.0 \times 10^{-2}$ mol dm⁻³, $[\text{H}^+] = 0.5$ mol dm⁻³. Pseudo-first order plots were made wherever reaction conditions permitted and the rate constants (k' , s⁻¹) were found to be independent of the initial concentrations of chromium(vi). Initial rates (k_i , mol dm⁻³ s⁻¹) were also computed by employing plane-mirror method¹⁰ where concentrations of the reactants were comparable.

Mannitol dependence : The concentrations of mannitol (Mtol) was varied in the range $(1.0\text{--}10.0) \times 10^{-2}$ mol dm⁻³ at fixed concentrations of other reaction ingredients viz. $[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm⁻³, $[\text{H}^+] = 0.5$ mol dm⁻³ and 30,

35 and 40 °C respectively. The rate increases with increasing concentration of mannitol and then tends to attain a limiting value at higher concentrations of alcohol.

Hydrogen ion dependence : The concentration of hydrogen ion was varied from 0.5 to 2.0 mol dm⁻³ keeping constant concentrations of other reaction ingredients viz. [Cr^{VI}] = 2.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [Mtol] = 2.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, and *I* = 2.0 mol dm⁻³ (ionic strength (*I*) was adjusted to be 2.0 mol dm⁻³ by employing lithium perchlorate). The rate of the reaction increases with increasing hydrogen ion concentration.

Fig. 2. A plot of $(k')^{-1}$ versus $[Mtol]^{-1}$: $[Cr^{VI}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm⁻³; $[HClO_4] = 0.5$ mol dm⁻³; temp. = (O) 30°; (Δ) 35° and (●) 40°C.

The variation in ionic strength was made by employing lithium perchlorate at constant concentrations of other components of the reaction mixture viz. [Cr^{VI}] = 2.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [Mtol] = 2.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³ and [H⁺] = 0.5 mol dm⁻³. The increase in five fold concentration of lithium perchlorate shows insignificant change in the rate of the reaction.

Chromium(III) dependence : The concentration of chromium(III) was varied from .10 × 10⁻³ to 5.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ at fixed concentrations of other reaction ingredients viz. [Cr^{VI}] = 2 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [Mtol] = 5.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³ and [H⁺] = 0.5 mol dm⁻³. The rate is independent of chromium(III) concentration ascribing to the fact that the rate determining step is not preceded via any fast equilibrium involving chromium(III).

Fig. 3. A plot (k') versus $((k_{Cr} - k')/[Cl^-])$: $[Cr^{VI}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3}$ mol dm⁻³; $[Mtol] = 0.5$ mol dm⁻³; $[Mtol] = 2.0 \times 10^{-2}$ mol dm⁻³; temp. = 35 °C.

The addition of large concentrations of acrylic acid during the progress of the reaction does not show formation of any white mass sediment and this eliminates possibility of involvement of free radicals in the reaction. The concentration of chloride ion was varied from 2.0 × 10⁻² to 5.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³ at fixed concentrations of other reaction ingredients viz. [Cr^{VI}] = 2.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [Mtol] = 2.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ and [H⁺] = 0.5 mol dm⁻³. The rate decreases tremendously with increasing concentration of chloride ion. Such an effect of chloride ion envisages that the chloro-chromium(vi) complex or complexes are formed with reduced reactivity towards mannitol. Therefore, this effect of chloride ion necessitates the analysis of not only the nature of such chloro-chromium(vi) species but their impact on the overall rate of the reaction.

Discussion

Chromium(vi) species in acid medium more or less are governed by the concentration of hydrogen ion via equilibria (2)–(6), the equilibrium constants have already been reported¹¹.

When the concentrations of chromium(vi) in aqueous solutions are greater than $5.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7^{2-}$ and its protonated forms are predominant. In case of lower concentrations of chromium(vi) and also lower hydrogen ion concentrations in the range of $(1.0-3.0) \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, the monomer HCrO_4^- predominates. However, if the hydrogen ion concentration is $>0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, the protonated form of the monomer becomes predominant species and is governed¹²⁻¹⁴ by the equilibrium (7).

The species HCrO_3^+ has also been assumed to be the reactive form of chromium(vi) in the oxidation of secondary alcohols⁴. The mechanism¹⁴ of oxidation of dimethyl sulphoxide by chromium(vi) has been supported by the overall hydrolytic and protolytic equilibrium (8).

Thus the reactive form of chromium(vi) in oxidation of mannitol in view of hydrogen ion concentration and its effect on the rate in all probability is HCrO_3^+ . This species has also been considered to be the reactive form of chromium in the oxidation of dimethyl sulphoxide¹⁴ and *N*-substituted phenothiazines.

Since the rate dependence on the concentration of mannitol exhibits a complex dependence, it simply accounts for a complex formation between the oxidant and the substrate. Thus considering HCrO_3^+ to be the reactive form of chromium(vi) and mannitol in its molecular form, the following reaction mechanism consisting of the following reaction steps (9-10) can be envisaged.

Such a mechanism leads to the rate law (11) or (12).

$$\frac{2}{3} \left[\frac{-d[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]}{dt} \right] = \frac{kK[\text{HCrO}_4^-][\text{Mtol}][\text{H}^+]^2}{(1 + K[\text{Mtol}])} \quad (11)$$

$$k' = \frac{kK[\text{Mtol}][\text{H}^+]^2}{1 + K[\text{Mtol}]} \quad (12)$$

where k' is an observed pseudo-first order rate constant.

A plot of k' versus $[\text{H}^+]^2$ was made from eq. (12) that yield a straight line (Fig. 1) passing through the origin conforming to the second order with respect to hydrogen ion concentration in accordance to the rate law (12). However, reciprocal of eq. (12) on rearrangement yields eq. (13).

$$\frac{1}{k'} = \frac{1}{kK[\text{Mtol}][\text{H}^+]^2} + \frac{1}{kK[\text{H}^+]^2} \quad (13)$$

A plot of $(k')^{-1}$ versus $[\text{Mtol}]^{-1}$ was further made from eq. (13) that also yielded a straight line with non-zero intercept (Fig. 2). The ratio of the intercept and slope of the line gave the value of K to be 6.3 ± 0.2 , 4.8 ± 0.2 and $3.2 \pm 0.1 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ at $I = 0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and 30, 35 and 40 °C respectively. The composite rate constant (kK) was calculated from the intercept to be $(2.0 \pm 0.2) \times 10^{-2}$, $(3.8 \pm 0.5) \times 10^{-2}$ and $(6.7 \pm 1.0) \times 10^{-2} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ at 30, 35 and 40 °C respectively at $I = 0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

So far as the mode of electron transfer from the substrate to the oxidant is concerned, the probable reaction (Scheme 1) can be envisaged. Levitt¹² in analysing the common characteristics of chromium(vi) oxidations of organic compounds in polar solvents reported that (-)vely charged species of chromium(vi) are rarely reactive. The electron deficient cationic species such as HCrO_3^+ or H_3CrO_4^+ or a highly polar molecule $\text{Cr}^{\delta+}\text{O}_3^{\delta-}$ were considered to be more reactive species and were supposed to undergo two-electron transfer in aqueous acid medium. Thus the intermediate ester undergoes a change of two-electrons during the decomposition yielding Cr^{IV} . Since Cr^{IV} is highly unstable and will intract with Cr^{VI} to form Cr^{V} , the later being more reactive intermediate than Cr^{VI} will immediately react with alcohol yielding aldehyde and chromium(III).

A glycol containing primary or secondary hydroxy groups undergoes oxidation to aldehyde or ketone by chromium(vi) rather than yielding a product with C-C cleavage². Therefore, the mode of interaction of chromium(vi) with mannitol can be envisaged as in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

The cleavage of chromium-oxygen bond in the intermediate takes place heterolytically due to accumulation of (+)ve charge on the chromium atom. Since such a charge accumulation is primarily due to the presence of the protons, the observed hydrogen ion catalysis can be accounted for this proposition. Further acrylic acid or acrylonitrile is not polymerized in the reaction mixture, this rules out any possibility of formation of free radicals. Nevertheless, Cr^V interaction with the substrate should yield a free-radical in one-equivalent change. Alcohols are reported¹⁻³ to undergo one-electron or two-electron transfer in oxidation by chromium(vi) and in later case the initial product of the metal ion is Cr^{IV} which either reacts with the substrate giving a free radical or interacts with the oxidant giving Cr^V. Since free-radicals are not trapped in the reaction mixture, the possibility of Cr^{IV} substrate reaction does not appear to be a reasonable mode of the reaction. Therefore, the formation of Cr^V appears to be the logical mode and this reacts in a two-equivalent step with the substrate eliminating any chances of the formation of free radicals. Such observations and the kinetic results hardly help in distinguishing^{16,17} between Cr^{IV} and Cr^V despite the fact that the redox potential of Cr^V/Cr^{VI} couple is much higher than that of the Cr^{IV}/Cr^V redox couple and this also supports the view that Cr^V intervenes in the reaction.

Chloride ion dependence : Anions including chloride ion are known to inhibit the oxidation reactions of chromium(vi) by complexing the metal ion. The chloro chromium(vi) species CrO₃Cl⁻ is reportedly¹⁸ formed that reduces the concentration of chromium(vi) and the concentration of the former species is governed by the equilibrium step (14).

If Cl⁻ inhibition at constant hydrogen ion concentration is taken into account, the empirical rate law (15) can be derived.

$$\text{Rate} = k_{\text{Cr}} [\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}][\text{Mtol}] + k_{\text{Cl}} [\text{CrO}_3\text{Cl}^-] [\text{Mtol}] \quad (15)$$

where k_{Cr} and k_{Cl} are the rate constants in the absence and presence of chloride ion. Substituting the concentration of Cr^{VI} in terms of total concentration from eq. (14) into eq. (15), eq. (17) on re-arrangement is obtained.

$$[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]_{\text{T}} = [\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}] + [\text{CrO}_3\text{Cl}^-]$$

$$k' = k_{\text{Cl}} + \frac{1}{K_{\text{Cl}}} \left[\frac{k_{\text{Cr}} - k''}{[\text{Cl}^-]} \right] \quad (17)$$

where k'' is an observed rate constant in the presence of chloride ion.

A plot of k'' versus $\left[\frac{k_{\text{Cr}} - k''}{[\text{Cl}^-]} \right]$ was made from eq. (17) that yielded a straight line with non-zero intercept (Fig. 3). K_{Cl} was calculated from the gradient to be $29 \pm 4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ at 35 °C and $I = 0.5 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ in agreement with the value reported earlier ($\sim 17 \pm 2.0$ at $I = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and 25 °C)¹⁰⁻²⁰, if temperature and ionic strength are any guide.

However, if CrO₃Cl⁻ species is not an oxidant for the substrate and the effect of the chloride ion is owing to the equilibrium shift only the eq. (18) should hold.

$$\text{Rate} = k_{\text{Cr}}[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}] \quad (18)$$

Considering eqs. (14) and (15), eq. (18) changes to eq. (19) or (20),

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{k_{\text{Cr}} [\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]_{\text{T}}}{1 + K' [\text{Cl}^-]} \quad (19)$$

$$\text{or } k'' = k_{\text{Cr}}/1 + K'[\text{Cl}^-] \quad (20)$$

where k'' is pseudo-first order rate constant in the presence of chloride ion.

A plot of $(k'')^{-1}$ against $[\text{Cl}^-]$ from eq. (20) yielded a curve, instead of, a straight line envisaging a separate pathway for CrO₃Cl⁻ species. Such a rate behaviour in all probability rules out any simple shift in equilibrium by the chloride ion concentration and, therefore, confirms CrO₃Cl⁻ species to be the reactive species of Cr^{VI} in the presence of chloride ion.

Another interesting but indirect conclusion regarding the complex formation between mannitol and chromium(vi) was obtained by the observed effect of chloride ion on the rate of the reaction. As is evident that chloro-chromium(vi) species are formed in the presence of chloride ion, the later has preference for co-ordination with Cr^{VI} to alcohol. Thus the preferential occupation of the co-ordination sites of Cr^{VI} by chloride ions inhibits further accommodation of alcohol in the co-ordination shell of the metal ion. Had the mannitol occupied co-ordination sites preferentially to chloride ion, the later should not affect the rate of the reaction as pronouncing as is observed experimentally.

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